

Sakadoj de la granda lemuria

SSak1 Let there be a sequence ℓ with an induced preorder ϕ , and write the composition as $\phi \circ \ell^{-1}$ as $\phi:\ell$. Denote the ordinality of $\phi:\ell$ as γ . Further, assume that there is a valuation on $\phi:\ell$,

$$\tau := \phi:\ell \rightarrow L_{|\{F\}|}$$

where for every $f \in F$, there is a bijection $\gamma(f) \leftrightarrow l \in \phi:\ell$. Call $\phi:\ell$ a "sentence", and suppose that F is a sheaf composed by "gluing" together rings of anisotropic (read: *polyserial*) gradations of typed existential quantifiers. I.e.,

$$\{F_e\}_{e \in E} \leftrightarrow \exists \tau_e \in T,$$

such that every member of the scheme E receives a corresponding polymodal index in T .

SEx.1 Say there is a sentence $\sqcup^2:\{a,b,\dots,h\}$, where $\phi = \sqcup^2$ is the disjoint union mod 2, or in other words a bi-regular enumeration. Then, let us suppose that such an operator induces the preorder

$$\sqcup^2 \leftrightarrow \{a=b\} \cong \{c=d\} \cong \{e=f\} \cong \{g=h\},$$

where the symbol \cong is generic, quasi-periodic, and liberal, meaning that the equivalence between members of sets $\{A\} \cong \{C\}$ is superficial, and is therefore class-level.

Then, say we have some rule, **r**, which reads as follows:

$$\frac{XYZ \leftrightarrow T_r}{x \cong y \cong z}$$

A possible interpretation of this rule is that the sentence formed by $\sqcup^2:l,m \in X; n,o \in Y; p,q \in Z$ is *strongly true* if for $\gamma(p_f)$, $f \in F_p \leftrightarrow \exists \tau_p \in T$. In other words, the sentence is true if the *order of the letters* of the sentence (l,m , etc.) is compatible with the

order of the words (X, Y, Z) , and thus there is a one-to-one correspondence between the truth values of each term and their ordering.

So, let us take the following (English) sentence:

"The big red dog has a nice hat."
 X Y Z α

The following sentence:

"The dog has hat."
 X Y Z α

while syntactically flawed, is technically correct if the first one is, as it respects the ordering of truth values, and so is equally correct. However, the sentence:

"The hat has red"
 X α Z Y

is not isomorphic to the other two, as the correspondence between the sentence $\sqcup^2:XYZ\alpha$ and the truth values $f_{x\alpha zY}$ are mismatched.

SRm.1 There are easy examples of real cases, even in traditional linguistics, where this construction fails; for instance, the truth values of words may be flexible, and subject to either some reordering, or tense, strict, and granular. In either case, we may construct a more abstract notion of "order" corresponding to chunks which map to certain referents. We simply need to change our preorder type; change our rules.

SSak2 Write **Viz.** for the category of visions; objects in this category are to be written $\mathbf{X}_p|_F$; they are called "viewpoints" and morphisms $\mathbf{X}_p|_F \rightarrow \mathbf{X}_{p'}|_{F'}$ represent transformations of internal truth values through the projective modulation of valuations; they are called **sakadoj** (*saccades*).

In "Concept Spaces for Mathematicians," I conjectured that there is an equivalence between the maps $\mathbf{X}_p \rightarrow \mathbf{X}_{p'}$, and the saccades of Viz. The proof was rather mangled, and toed the lines of "woo-woo" territory; here, I hope that this statement

has by now become so obvious as to warrant no proof whatsoever, although I will provide one nonetheless.

SPF.1 We want to show that for two sentences $\phi:\ell$ and $(\phi:\ell)'$, if either ϕ or ℓ are varied, then $L_{|\{F\}|}$ varies in a similar fashion. First, the variation need not always be marked; for instance, take the trivial variation. Say we have an (incoherent Esperanto) sentence

a a a a a a,

for which the preorder is disjoint union mod 3. Say $(\phi:\ell)'$ is

a a a a a a a a a a a a,

for which the new preorder is disjoint union mod 6. Then, because the first sentence is an Abelian subgroup of the second, the corresponding truth evaluation is identical in F_{12} .

Suppose instead we have

Aba

mod $x=2$.

Then, we have $\phi:\ell \rightarrow \gamma(f_1, f_3)$. Next, let $\phi \rightarrow \phi'$ be given by letting $x \rightarrow 1$. The corresponding inclusion $\gamma_1(\ell) \rightarrow \gamma(f_1, f_3)$ is equivalent to $\gamma_2(\ell) \rightarrow \gamma(f_1, f_2, f_3)$ with the axiom of choice and the pigeonhole principle. Thus, the inclusion $\phi:\ell \hookrightarrow F$ is shown to be injective, and therefore a true isomorphism.